

Language Teaching Methods in Intercultural Classrooms

Annotation:

The intercultural language classroom creates a clear multicultural learning environment, and teachers must assist students in comprehending and appreciating the distinctions and similarities that exist among many ethnic, religious and cultural groups. The aim of this article is to find out what are the language teaching strategies used in promoting and enhancing successful multicultural interactions. This study is based on the strategies used by English teachers for teaching students in multicultural classes. This research represents a qualitative study, in which several multicultural classroom practices and instructional methods were examined, as well as earlier research articles by other researchers.

Keywords:

intercultural, strategies, methods, cultural, teaching, multicultural, cultural background, student, culture, foreign language, learning.

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Introduction

Humanbeings acquire their mother tongue as they grow naturally. In case of second or foreign language learning, they need a kind of training or classroom teaching. Teaching is a complex procedure. However, it may be even more challenging in intercultural classrooms. Cultural diversity in classroom is on the rise. In our increasingly diverse and multicultural society, it's more important than ever for teachers to incorporate culturally responsive instruction in the classroom – whether teaching elementary school, middle school or high school students.

Teaching in intercultural classroom is one of the major issues of language teaching. The majority of the classroom in our context consists of multicultural groups where students have different needs and learning styles. In such classrooms, students are individually unique and they are different from others due to the factors including language, culture, age, race and ethnicity.

Different social backgrounds, environment and culture influence the process of language acquisition. Students are different in terms of experience, methods of learning and many other factors, all of which impact the students' behaviour and their learning styles. Teaching in such diverse classroom providing equal access in materials resources and opportunities in classroom activities and ensuring success of all students are really the complex issues for the language teachers. Besides, different challenges of intercultural classroom, it has also some positive aspects. For example, heterogeneous classroom may enrich the variety of social interaction, more life experiences and knowledge, more options, interests and ideas but it also creates situations that challenge teachers' resourcefulness while trying to give each student an opportunity to learn a language. The common challenges in heterogeneous classes are, how to cope with the discipline, how to change heterogeneous students' attitude and develop motivation, what methods and techniques to be chosen to teach them. Moreover, what strategies can be

used to teach the students of such nature if they do not want to talk, if classes are big, if students keep using their own language?

Having the above mentioned issues in consideration and curiosity of finding the strategies used for teaching such types of students, this study is going to be carried out in the title “Language teaching methods in intercultural classroom”.

Research Methods

This research represents a qualitative study, in which several strategies and teaching methods used in multicultural classes were viewed and previous articles by other researchers were observed.

Good and professional teachers use a different kind of teaching methods in order to stimulate all their students’ learning. For instance, relying on stereotypes regarding one’s race or ethnicity is not a proper way to create a teaching plan for students of that culture (Davis, 2013).

Another aspect of creating a good atmosphere in a multicultural classroom should be based on establishing a friendly relationship between a teacher and students, since students in authoritarian classrooms are more likely to give negative feedback or might feel threatened for being different. In order to avoid this, a teacher should behave like a facilitator in the classroom, not like an instructor (Lynch, 2015). Creating a survey to decide what is the most interesting for student and what fits their needs might be a good way to show them that they are actually the ones who help the teacher decide and gives them motivation to learn, once they had a chance to choose and be recognized as an important factor in making decisions.

Usually, students with different cultural background, non-native speakers of the language spoken in that country might feel lost and unaccepted, those feelings pressuring them to push their native language aside and forcing them to consider target language as their main language. In a culturally responsive classroom, it is important to celebrate varieties and help non- native speakers realise that diversity is an advantage and that it enriches the whole classroom. That is the perfect method to help students achieve fluency in target language without feeling uncomfortable. Even the usage of students’ native language in some materials might be very helpful in language learning. Teachers should know how to incorporate materials related to their students’ diversities into everyday classes and make them feel accepted and thus encourage students to develop a sense of identity based on their differences. Teachers are important helping students not to feel like they are on their own, but have a friend in their teacher.

Cohen (1931, p. 34) believes that group work is the best strategies to teach heterogeneous class. The interest in individual student is the key to a heterogeneous class satisfaction. Students come to the school with different ideas, expectation and needs. Therefore, they should look at as individuals and not as a whole class. Various grouping strategies such as grouping students according to qualifications/programs should be done by teachers. This helps to tend to their needs, for example in the language use, grammar and language skills in language learning. At other instances a teacher may divide students according to their abilities if the learning outcome requires that. Also, group dynamics need to be taken into consideration when grouping students together. Moreover, background and a proficiency level play a central role as well when grouping students. A curriculum is quite often underestimated for its importance in teaching, but it is crucial for a good pedagogic approach to academic performances. Even the simplest curriculum is important because it defines what is chosen as the best literature, authors, and texts for students, and what is the best to use in order to help students value their own culture and history (Davis, 2013). What is important is that all students in a group should be active participants, cooperating with their fellow members in all given activities. This will ensure that they are learning effectively. Balancing a group helps prevent the Halo Effect by the teacher and those who are proficient are expected to offer support to students that require help. This

diverse nature of students in one class is stimulating and calls for the teacher to be innovative and creative in order to have a "coherent" class.

Results and discussion

The primary purpose of this study was to examine the cultural challenges in learning a foreign language in diverse schools. Previous results suggest that there are many differences in teaching, also various methods and approaches used depending on the students' cultural and ethnical backgrounds because each student required different attention and support in learning.

The results presented the various approaches to students who are from different cultural background and how they are regarded as neglected compared to other students. By having a diverse classroom, grouping the learners by various types of topics of interest and level of expertise, integrating some gamification elements to foster the discussion and knowledge sharing, peer-learning, include problem solving and inquiry teaching method.

Conclusion

This study found that the student's ethnical and cultural background played an important role in their overall learning experience. An important role concerning students of diverse cultures has the teacher. The results are in line with the results of McCombs (2001) and Newman (2002) who found that students who feel they have supportive and caring teachers are more motivated to engage in academic work than students with unsupportive and uncaring teachers. Indeed, teachers who learn more about their students' backgrounds, cultures, and experiences will feel more capable and efficient in their work as teachers and have less difficulty with their students acquiring the English language. During classroom interactions, teachers should keep the special cultural needs of their diverse student in mind, also some educators believe that all children benefit from inclusion because it creates an authentic microcosm of the society students will be participating in once they finish school (Karten, 2010; Rea, McLaughlin, & Walther-Thomas, 2002).

Most of the time students have their own purposes for learning or achieving specific goals within a class (Rizvić & Bećirović, 2017). It is very important to focus on the learning outcomes the teacher wants learners to achieve besides their individual background. Having a classroom with diverse learners is a wonderful opportunity to share knowledge and enrich the classroom and learning experience through different expertise. The 21st century skills aim that learners experience learning across curriculum, meaning that the same topic can be analysed from various perspectives.

Teachers can improve lives of their students, and they should work hard on that. They can also help in making the multicultural classroom more pleasant place to be in, by changing their approaches to learning. «Being flexible is one of the most important aspects of teaching students of diverse cultures (Doyle, 2006). It is of great importance for teachers to investigate the issues of any kind inside the classroom and related to learning processes and to help students reduce the problems, to help students to improve their academic achievements and create a strong relationship with students.

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